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Interactive Media for STEM Education

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Abstract: *This study examines the importance of STEM subjects and optimal ways of teaching them. The results of research showed that interactive media devices, if used with professional teaching techniques, can be one of the main components of STEM curriculum because they provide students with interactive learning environments, fostering their curiosity and leading to better learning outcomes. Consequently, students with solid STEM background can contribute to the development of new technologies, economic growth and medical advancements, improving quality of life in society overall.*

Key words: *STEM subjects, Interactive Media tools, Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), Simulations tools, better learning outcomes.*

Introduction

STEM subjects are often given a high value because of their contribution to the development of analytical and soft skills among students. This importance is further highlighted by the labour demand for people specializing in STEM fields. Consequently, it is necessary to build a well-crafted curriculum to ensure the best engagement of students and quality education in STEM subjects. However, with the traditional teaching methods and approaches which were invented centuries ago, most teachers are struggling to deliver highly rigorous STEM curriculums, let alone fostering the curiosity and interest in students for these subjects. Therefore, considering the ever-growing importance of STEM disciplines in the success of prospective students, teachers should seek innovative and far more efficient ways of teaching those subjects.

Learning STEM subjects is evidently an inseparable part of school curriculum for several reasons. Firstly, grasping the advanced level concepts in mathematics or involving in hands-on experiments, students will be able to nurture strong problem-solving, critical thinking and teamworking skills. Additionally, advantages of STEM disciplines are not limited to those apparent skills. For example, constant exposure to hard mathematical problems can help students to manage academic stress,

making them more resilient and enduring. Experiences students get from learning STEM disciplines are highly valued in job market, meaning that they contribute immensely to the future success of students. Thus, schools and teachers are responsible for creating a positive and stimulating learning environment that sets students up for future workplace.

School is a place where students evolve from very early age until college life, making it one of the most important stages of their life. Most high school students will continue with the major they choose during high school, and this is immensely affected by teachers' techniques, resources and tools used in the classrooms. However, traditional STEM classrooms often involve passive learning, where teachers give lectures on particular topics with minimal student engagement. This is also true for other STEM subjects including biology, chemistry or computer science. Traditional approaches towards teaching STEM curriculum are limited to only theoretical knowledge with very little to no practical learning. This makes it so hard for school children to actually understand the complex topics and creates an unstimulating learning environment. Ultimately, students who chose their major in STEM will go to colleges with very little practical knowledge and less-developed essential skills, which also contributes to their poor performance at workplace later in the future (Felder, 2021, p. 8)

Thus, in order to prevent poor performance of STEM students, teachers should seek innovative ways of keeping students engaged during classes. Delivering the new concepts effectively during STEM classes should also be the main concern for teachers. One of the optimal ways of dealing with these difficult situations is incorporating new technologies into classroom settings. One such promising field is Interactive media which offers range of tools for teachers to utilize during STEM classes.

Interactive media is one of the fast-developing fields of today's world with various tools and devices. It is widely used in different sectors of society, including educational sector. When skilfully integrated into STEM classrooms, interactive media means can devise creative and stimulating environment and knowledge construction. They also help students to have wider range of opportunities when learning STEM subjects (Jibrán, Vahidy, 2019). For example, interactive media tools can be used as simulations tools, Augmented Reality (AR) or Virtual Reality (VR) devices which create visual images and virtual exposure to what STEM students are learning in books. By expertly using these recent technological means during STEM sessions, teachers will be able to nurture curiosity in students to STEM fields and be able to provide with better learning experiences, all which lead to greater student outcomes.

In STEM classrooms, teachers can implement variety of technological tools ranging from simulation tools to gaming instructions, which essentially require student engagement. Considering the fact that almost all STEM subjects have classes in which hands-on experiment are main component of learning process, simulation tools, for example, can be helpful for various reasons. In classes like chemistry, physics or anatomy, real equipment or instruments can be hard to obtain and even dangerous to use in a classroom setting, such as working with chemical compounds during chemistry lesson. However, simulation models will enable students to have the same learning and practicing environment, with safety and affordable tools (Jibrán, Vahidy, 2019).

Additionally, the use of recent technologies such as Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) makes learning process more immersive for students (Jibrán, Vahidy, 2019). Augmented Reality is using digital information in the forms of videos, images and text graphics, while VR tools immerse users into a simulated environment where they can explore objects in 3D forms. For example, in a biology class, students can view the images of heart in 3D form, making the experience more interactive and memorable. Also, engineering students can create a virtual lab by VR tools and explore

different concepts in real time, which can add more depth into their learning process. Increased engagement and learning experience, at the same time, affect teacher's overall motivation to educate and make their job less stressful. By integrating those features of Interactive media in their classrooms, both teachers and students can get equal number of benefits.

A research experiment published in Randwick International of Education and Linguistics Science (RIELS) studied the effect of interactive multimedia on learning STEM subjects. Based on the results of direct observations and interviews conducted at SD Negeri 104197 Klambir Village, focusing on 30 fifth grade students, researchers found that interactive media means improved student learning outcomes and retention significantly. 28 students out of total 30 demonstrated positive results during post-tests, supporting the idea that technological tools used during classrooms effectively attracted student's attention and led to better learning outcomes. Additionally, these tools could be adjusted by teachers to the needs of each student, ensuring the equally engaging learning environment.

It is essential to mention that Interactive media tools improve the learning outcomes with creating visual experiences that can add more depth to understanding of complex STEM topics. They also play a huge role in keeping students motivated and interested in STEM subject, which is an essential part of teaching process.

Given the significant role that teaching STEM has on students' future success, it is essential to find new and effective approaches of educating students. Interactive media means can assist teachers significantly by delivering the knowledge in a stimulative way and keeping students engaged. It is also important to adjust tools and devices according to the needs of students and different subject types, so that both student and teachers can get the fullest benefit from Interactive media tools.

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